

Advancing Sodium-Ion Battery Cathode Analysis With Cryogenic Ag-coated APT Specimens

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Abstract

Layered oxide cathodes have attracted wide research interest due to their controllable synthesis, tuneability, and high energy density in sodium-ion batteries (SIBs). However, in layered oxide cathodes, capacity retention is unsatisfactory due to structural changes, and the severity of capacity fading increases at higher voltages. Chemical heterogeneity and concentration gradient lead to the co-existence of multiple phases with lattice mismatch and strain development. To achieve the practical usage of high-density and low-cost layered oxide cathodes for SIBs, it is very important to develop an atomic-scale understanding of the compositional changes in the multi-component cathode. Atom probe tomography (APT) is a very promising technique to analyze chemical composition and heterogeneity in three dimensions (3D) with high spatial resolution and brings insights into possible property- or lifetime-limiting factors. However, APT is underpinned by an intense electric field that can drive preferential alkali metal outward migration and cause *in situ* de-intercalation of alkali metals that makes APT analysis challenging. As a first report, we show that silver (Ag) coating on SIB cathode APT specimens, deposited inside the focused-ion beam (FIB) at cryogenic temperature, allows for analysis of the compositional heterogeneity in air-sensitive sodium-ion-layered oxide cathode material.

Key words: sodium-ion battery, battery cathodes, cryogenic focused ion beam, *in situ* FIB metal coating, atom probe tomography

Introduction

Sodium-ion batteries (SIBs) are ubiquitous choices to support the energy transition from nonrenewable energy resources in terms of safety, reaction kinetics, wider operating temperature range, and sustainability compared to lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) (Liang et al., 2023; Zuo et al., 2023). The energy density of the state-of-the-art batteries is limited by the low capacity of the cathode active materials. It is impossible to directly replicate chemistry from LIB cathodes. Cathodes with earth-abundant elements in SIBs are of great importance due to cost-effectiveness and sustainability (Chen et al., 2019; Kim et al., 2024). Cobalt (Co) is required for crystal structure stabilization in layered oxide cathodes for LIBs. Inversely, Co-free layered oxide cathodes are structurally possible in SIBs and are favorable in terms of price and sustainability compared to LIBs (Radin et al., 2017; Chen et al., 2019; Yu et al., 2023). However, in layered oxide cathodes, capacity retention is subpar due to structural and compositional changes over increasing charge/discharge cycles. The strong Coulomb repulsion between adjacent Na⁺ sites forms an unfavorable ordered arrangement of Na⁺/vacancy resulting in strong Na⁺ diffusion barriers, multiple charge–discharge plateaus, and severe deterioration of electrochemical performance (Wen et al., 2015; Radin et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2020). Compositional heterogeneity created during different depths of charge/discharge can lead to non-uniform potential distribution and a decrease in reaction reversibility (Wang et al., 2020; Yu et al., 2023; Chen et al., 2024). In Li-based cathode materials,

studies have mostly reported changes at the surface and in the near-surface region, not as much in the bulk, which has very different structures, electrochemical redox behavior, and degradation mechanisms (Hayashi et al., 2014; Kim et al., 2016; Chae et al., 2021).

The atomic-scale understanding of transition metal dissolution and chemical heterogeneity is scarcely available for SIB oxide cathodes. To develop an optimized, commercially viable SIB cathode, deeper knowledge of the evolution of cathode properties with chemical heterogeneities is required.

Atom probe tomography (APT) is a very effective tool to study phase and chemical segregation in three dimensions with sub-nanometer resolution (Larson et al., 2013; Gault et al., 2012, 2021). APT has an equivalent chemical sensitivity across the periodic table, and the chemical sensitivity and spatial distribution of lighter elements like Li and H can be assessed, which is typically challenging for electron- and X-ray-based techniques (Gault et al., 2024). Accurate analysis of battery materials using APT remains challenging though, due to (i) sensitivity to environmental exposure (Kim, Antonov, et al., 2022; Singh et al., 2023), including moisture trapping or surface hydroxide formation along with Na⁺/H⁺ exchange in Na-based cathode materials (Maier et al., 2016; Pfeiffer et al., 2017); (ii) the relatively low thermal and electrical conductivity of oxide electrode material that can cause local heating, degraded mass resolution, and sample fracture before significant data collection (Kölling & Vandervorst, 2009; Bok et al., 2016; Prosa et al., 2019); (iii) electromigration or *in situ*

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de-lithiation caused by the intense electric field, required to field evaporate surface atoms, modifies the pristine distribution of atoms making their analysis challenging (Maier et al., 2016; Pfeiffer et al., 2017). Although a similar de-sodiation can be expected from materials with a high Na mobility, it has not been reported yet. Na distribution has been previously reported within materials without such issues being reported (Cadel et al., 2010; Choi et al., 2011; Hellmann et al., 2015; Lu et al., 2017), and the analysis of pure Na appeared possible, even if the point density within the reconstructed data was not fully homogeneous (Yoo et al., 2022). Battery materials are also highly sensitive to both air and beam exposure. Interaction with electron and ion beams can induce whisker formation, and focused-ion beam (FIB) sample preparation affects the chemical composition (Ding et al., 2023; Singh et al., 2023). In our preliminary trials using conventional Ga-FIB protocols, Ga incorporation was observed at concentrations exceeding 17 at% throughout the specimen volume (Supplementary Fig. S1).

To circumvent these challenges, specimen transfer using ultrahigh vacuum (UHV) cryogenic shuttle from an inert gas-filled glove box, cryo sample preparation, and *in situ* metallic coating protocols in the scanning electron microscope-focused ion beam (SEM-FIB) have been developed for air and beam-sensitive materials (Stephenson et al., 2018; Woods et al., 2023). Here, specimens were prepared at cryogenic temperatures to minimize the beam damage during FIB milling and preserve the structure and composition of the material of interest (Schwarz et al., 2024).

Another challenge in APT analysis lies in the high fields during sample run, which can drive preferential migration and evaporation of certain elements, further complicating analysis (Kim, Antonov, et al., 2022). Recently, based on preliminary work by Kölling et al. (Kölling & Vandervorst, 2009), an approach for *in situ* metallic coating has been introduced for capping the needle-shaped specimens inside the SEM-FIB at the end of the preparation (Schwarz et al., 2024), which improved data quality and yield, enabling the analysis of a range of complex materials, including MXenes and LIB electrode materials (Woods et al., 2023; Krämer et al., 2024; Singh et al., 2024).

Here, APT specimens were prepared from a $\text{Na}_{2/3}\text{Ni}_{1/6}\text{Fe}_{1/6}\text{Mn}_{2/3}\text{O}_2$ single-crystal-layered oxide cathode using a fully cryogenic workflow, including UHV transfer, cryo-FIB lift-out method, and cryo-sharpening followed by metallic coating of the final APT specimens within the FIB.

Previous reports suggest that Cr is a versatile metal for *in situ* coating approaches. However, it is not suitable for our material of interest due to its high evaporation field, which is incompatible with Na-based oxide cathodes. It leads to premature specimen failure and, within limited datasets acquired, Cr and its oxides exhibit numerous overlapping peaks with the measured material, rendering the analysis of the mass spectrum unreliable and challenging. Through a systematic set of studies, we propose using a thin metallic Ag coating on the prepared APT specimen as a viable alternative. The present methodology facilitates the probing of air- and beam-sensitive SIB oxide cathode without surface exposure, degradation, premature fracture, or *in situ* de-sodiation. Our study opens new opportunities to analyze 3D compositional heterogeneity in oxide for SIBs and their correlation with electrochemical properties.

Materials and Methods

Cathode Synthesis

The oxide cathode was synthesized using the sol-gel method, followed by calcination. Briefly, $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (99.9%), $\text{Mn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (99.9%), $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (99.9%), and sodium nitrate (99.9%) (5% excess) sourced from Fisher Scientific GmbH were dissolved in deionized water. Citric acid was used as a chelating agent. The mixed solution was aged at 80°C until gel formation, and the obtained product was dried at 100°C in air. Then, the sample was heated at 450°C for 6 h, 900°C for 12 h, followed by annealing at 1050°C in air. The synthesized sample is labeled as $\text{Na}_{2/3}\text{Ni}_{1/6}\text{Fe}_{1/6}\text{Mn}_{2/3}\text{O}_2$ (NFMO) and transferred to the argon glove box from Syla Tech after synthesis.

Materials Characterization

X-Ray diffraction (XRD) measurements were conducted using a diffractometer Rikaku Smartlab 9KW with a Cu $K\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.154$ nm). SEM and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) measurements were performed using a Zeiss Sigma SEM at 18-kV and 5.4-nA current. Morphological and structural investigations were performed using Transmission electron microscopy (TEM), and selected area electron diffraction (SAED) analysis with JEOL2100 plus, at a working voltage of 200 kV with LaB_6 electron source. Samples for TEM analysis were drop-cast onto a holey carbon TEM grid and immediately transferred to the microscope for further investigation.

APT Specimen Preparation Using Cryo-FIB

Within an N_2 -glovebox from SylaTech (O_2 and H_2O level below 0.1 ppm), the cathode material and the supporting Si coupon (Cameca FT 36) were mounted onto a clip holder in a dual-post cryogenic atom probe puck (Cameca Instruments, Madison, WI, USA). Afterward, the sample was transferred using an ultrahigh vacuum transfer shuttle (VCTM) from Ferrovac GmbH to the FIB (Stephenson et al., 2018). A Helios 5 CX Dual-Beam Ga-FIB/SEM (Thermo-Fisher Scientific Instruments) with easy lift cryo-micromanipulator was used to lift out a lamella of cathode material under cryogenic conditions with a target temperature of -190°C , using the protocol described by Woods et al. (2023). For the *in situ* metallic coating, a lamella of Ag or Cr was pre-attached to the manipulator at room temperature using the gas injection systems (GIS). The cathode specimen was mounted onto a series of commercial Si coupons and sharpened, following the first steps of the protocol outlined in Ref. (Woods et al., 2023; Schwarz et al., 2024) and as illustrated in Supplementary Figure S2. The needle-shaped cathode specimen was coated with Cr or Ag using the procedure described in Ref. (Schwarz et al., 2024; Singh et al., 2024). *In situ* coating was performed at 30 kV and 40 pA for 30 s for Cr and at 30 kV and 24 pA for 20 s for Ag, with the stage rotated by 90° to ensure uniform coating from all four sides.

Atom Probe Tomography Measurement and Analysis

The uncoated and coated APT specimens were transferred to the APT instrument via the Ferrovac ultrahigh vacuum shuttle at cryogenic temperature (80 K) and through the air at room temperature, respectively. The data were acquired on a

Fig. 1. Characterization of the synthesized cathode material. (a) Powder X-ray diffraction obtained and calculated, (b) Bright-field TEM image, (c) SAED pattern from the encircled region in (b), (d-i) SEM-EDX mapping of Na, O, Mn, Ni, and Fe.

Cameca LEAP 5000XS APT at a base temperature of 50 K, pulse repetition rate of 125 kHz, and detection rate of 0.3–0.5 ions per 100 pulses on average. Laser pulse energy was varied from 5–15 pJ, as detailed below. Data analysis was done using AP Suite 6.3.

Results and discussion

Synthesized Single-crystal NFMO Cathode

Phase formation and crystal structure of the cathode material are characterized by XRD. Crystal structure matches with P2-type structure with a space group of $P6_3/mmc$ as shown in Figure 1a (Yoshida et al., 2014). The morphology and crystal structure of NFMO were analyzed using TEM bright-field images and SAED patterns. The TEM image in Figure 1b

shows plate-like morphology with a particle size in the range of 4–7 μm . The hexagonal dotted SAED pattern evidences the single-crystalline nature of NFMO in Figure 1c (Bi et al., 2020; Sun et al., 2021). SEM and elemental mapping by EDS of an NFMO particle is shown in Figure 1(d-i), which suggests a uniform distribution of Na, Ni, Fe, Mn, and O on the microscale. Additional SEM images and EDS data are provided in Supplementary Figure S3.

Environmental Stability of Oxide Cathode

Analysis of layered oxide cathodes is challenging due to their instability in moist air which leads to surface degradation (Wang et al., 2018). Comparative XRD data of pristine and air-exposed NFMO sample after 1 week in Figure 2 show

evidence of water intercalation into the interlayers and the formation of surface hydroxide phases, as indicated by the ‡ symbols. This type of environmental interaction is expected to be even more pronounced in APT specimens, which have a high surface-to-volume ratio. Thus, accurate characterization is not feasible using conventional protocols that involve sample preparation and transfer through air. To avoid such exposure, all transfers between the glove box, FIB, and APT were carried out using a vacuum suitcase under both room temperature and cryogenic conditions.

APT Analysis of Uncoated Cathode Specimen

APT Measurements were performed at a base temperature of 50 K, laser pulse energy of 20 pJ, pulse repetition rate of

Fig. 2. Environmental stability of cathode. Powder X-ray diffraction before (NFMO) and after air exposure (NFMO-AE).

125 kHz, and with a target detection rate of 0.5 ions per 100 pulses on average. During voltage increases, *in situ* de-sodiation (sodium migration to the surface) is observed, characterized by sudden bursts of Na ions. These events caused erratic drops and increases in the applied DC voltage, as marked by black arrows in Figure 3a. The sudden ion bursts led to periods where only Na⁺ ions were detected until these sodium sources were depleted. This behavior is similar to that reported for Li (Kim, El-Zoka, et al., 2022; Singh et al., 2024). Up to 97 at% Na can be observed in the mass spectrum in Figure 3b, and therefore, it was not possible to detect Ni, Fe, and Mn due to high evaporation field strengths compared to Na. The detector hit map and corresponding 3D reconstruction are shown in Figures 3c and 3d, respectively. Preferentially localized hot spots in the detector hit map also indicate non-homogenous field evaporation of cathode specimens. Additionally, porosity in the cathode particle made the APT specimen preparation and measurement more challenging (Barroo et al., 2020; Kim, El-Zoka, et al., 2022). These fine porosities act as stress concentration centers during the applied voltage, eventually leading to specimen failure. Fracture of the uncoated samples was frequent, limiting the volume of material that could be analyzed before sample failure occurred.

APT Analysis of Cr-coated Cathode Specimen

Electrochemical impregnation and liquid metal encapsulation methods have been proposed to fill the porosity and voids in APT specimens (Seol et al., 2016; Barroo et al., 2020; Kim et al., 2020; Kim, El-Zoka, et al., 2022). However, these methods expose the samples to harsh conditions, transport through air, ex-situ coating, and fill the porosity with a material that leads to a large number of peaks in the mass spectrum that

Fig. 3. APT data of uncoated cathode: (a) Voltage profile, (b) Mass spectrum, (c) Detector hit map, and (d) 3D reconstruction in x-z and x-y directions.

Fig. 4. APT data of Cr-coated cathode: (a) Voltage profile, (b) Mass spectrum; inset shows magnified spectrum, (c) the detector hit the map, (d) 3D reconstruction in the x - z and x - y direction.

can make the analysis of the mass spectrum much more complex. Moreover, it can lead to unwanted reactions between the cathode and medium that change the composition and result in uncertainties. Metallic coatings have been applied to various materials to enhance data collection and quality (Mosiman et al., 2021; Woods et al., 2023; Schwarz et al., 2024). This metallic coating can be deposited *in situ* during sample preparation in the FIB and under cryogenic conditions, making this approach suitable for air- and beam-sensitive materials. Cr-coating was reported to mitigate preferential evaporation of Li from NMC811 cathode particles or lithiated graphitic carbon fiber and improve data collection during APT measurement (Johansen et al., 2024; Singh et al., 2024).

Inspired by previous works successfully analyzing LIB electrode materials using metallic coating, we have *in situ* coated the SIB layered oxide cathode specimens with Cr following cryo-FIB sample preparation. APT measurements of the Cr-coated specimens were performed at a base temperature of 50 K, laser pulse energy of 15 pJ, pulse repetition rate of 100 kHz, and with a target detection rate of 0.5 ions per 100 pulses on average. Cr-coated specimens yielded relatively larger datasets, with reduced voltage fluctuations and fewer sudden ion bursts during field evaporation. Sample fracture, however, was still observed, as indicated by the steep voltage spike at the end of the voltage curve shown in Figure 4a. However, the higher evaporation field of Cr requires high voltage, resulting in premature sample fracture. The obtained mass spectrum, Figure 4b, showed very high counts of Na along with Cr containing species. The counts of other solute elements (i.e., Ni, Fe, and Mn) were quite less. The detector

hit map and corresponding 3D reconstruction are shown in Figures 4c and 4d, respectively. The hit density is more homogeneous than in the case of the uncoated specimens. The Cr-coating of the cathode specimens has shown an improvement in data compared to the uncoated measurements, however, the large difference in the electric field strength of Cr (27 V/nm) compared to Na (11 V/nm) led to preferential evaporation of Na. Also, the nature of the coating is not pure Cr, as pointed out by Schwarz et al. (Schwarz et al., 2024), and contains up to nearly 10 at% O, and can get further oxidized during the transfer through the ambient atmosphere, which results in a more complex mass spectrum. Cr oxides have several overlapping peaks with the cathode specimen, which creates a hurdle for accurate peak assignment during APT mass spectrum analysis (30–70 Da) (La Fontaine et al., 2015). Additionally, Cr-oxidation decreases the conductivity that results in poor heat dissipation and sample fracture. This made Cr-coating unsuitable for our purpose.

APT Analysis of Ag-coated Cathode Specimen

To overcome the abovementioned challenges, *in situ* Ag coating was used. Ag is selected for coating because of its relatively lower evaporation field (24 V/nm) than Cr (27–29 V/nm), leading to lower electrostatic pressures and stresses on the specimen and hence reducing the probability of failure (Wilkes et al., 1972; Tsong, 1978). Ag has only two isotopes, at a higher mass-to-charge ratio, i.e. 107 and 109 Da, avoiding overlaps with the peaks of most of the elements used in battery components (Kluthe et al., 2002) and facilitating accurate

Fig. 5. APT data of Ag-coated cathode: (a) detector hit map, (b) 3D reconstruction (left) and 1-D concentration profile from the marked area (right), (c) 3D atom reconstruction in x - z and x - y , (d) mass spectrum from the marked area of interest in figure (b), and data presented is from 15-pJ laser pulse energies.

peak assignment. The high electrical conductivity of Ag (6.2×10^7 S/m) compared to Cr (7.9×10^6 S/m) is beneficial in coating the tips for a successful APT run. In addition, Ag is relatively noble and can inhibit unwanted reactions with the cathode material, preserving its pristine structure and composition. Cathode specimens were prepared under cryogenic conditions and coated *in situ* with Ag. This Ag coating enabled the air transfer of the cathode sample without surface degradation/oxidation, eliminating the need for a UHV shuttle during sample transfer.

APT measurements were performed at a base temperature of 50 K, laser pulse energy of 5–15 pJ, a pulse repetition rate of 125 kHz, and a target detection rate of 0.3 ions per 100 pulses on average. Data collected at 15 pJ is presented in Figure 5. After the Ag coating, the field evaporation of the cathode material appeared more homogenous, and the absence of hot spots in detector hit maps indicates that the Ag coating has circumvented the electric field-induced preferential evaporation of

sodium, as shown in Figure 5a. The 3D reconstruction and a 1D composition profile calculated along the cylindrical region of interest marked in dark green are provided in Figure 5b. This region of interest was positioned to avoid the contribution of the coated Ag. When normalized to the metallic species, the 0.32 solute atom ratio of Na is comparable with the atomic ratio obtained from SEM-EDS. The solute atomic ratio of Na, Ni, Mn, and Fe is provided in Figure 6. Oxygen loss is observed in laser pulse APT measurement of all oxides. This loss can be attributed to molecular dissociation forming neutral O_2 molecules either that cannot be detected, or that have a time-of-flight no longer proportional to the applied specimen voltage, precluding their identification (Gault et al., 2016; Kim et al., 2024). The compositional homogeneity plays a critical role in the electrochemical performance of cathode materials. Heterogeneity leads to non-uniform potential distribution, anisotropic volume changes, and mechanical failure of the electrode (Kim et al., 2016). 3D elemental distribution of each

Fig. 6. Comparison of normalized solute atomic ratio of Na, Ni, Fe, and Mn from SEM-EDS, APT and theoretical.

element from the cathode specimen, including Ag- and Ga ions is provided in Figure 5c. Projections along the $x-z$ and $x-y$ planes demonstrates that Ag and Ga are mostly confined to the outer surface. During *in situ* FIB coatings, Ga ions co-deposited with Ag, forming the outer layer. As an outcome of low sputtering current and cryogenic conditions, the sample remained in its pristine state. As shown in Figure 5b, the Ga concentration within the analyzed volume is ~ 0.9 at%.

A homogenous distribution of Na, Ni, Fe, and Mn is observed in the Ag-coated cathode specimen. Slight non-homogeneity at the surface may be attributed to the preferential deposition of silver on one side. The mass spectrum from the marked region of interest is provided in Figure 5d (a magnified view is provided in Supplementary Fig. S4). The non-overlapping Ag peaks at 107 and 109 Da significantly improved the peak assignment and compositional analysis. A comparison of the voltage profiles for Cr-coated and Ag-coated cathode specimens is presented in Supplementary Figure S5. The voltage curve for the Ag-coated sample is smooth and with minor fluctuations, indicating uniform and stable evaporation. This is required to run the tip without premature fracture (0.6 million ions for the Cr-coated specimen) before significant data collection (5 million ions for Ag-coated specimen). The laser pulse energy was varied to 10 pJ, and the collected data are provided in Supplementary Figure S6, which also indicates uniformity of elemental distribution in 3D without preferential evaporation or segregation.

Conclusion and Perspective

In conclusion, this study demonstrates the successful implementation of cryogenic *in situ* Ag coating during cryo-FIB APT specimen preparation for oxide-layered cathode materials in SIBs. The use of Ag proves to be a suitable coating material due to its low redeposition sputtering current, non-reactivity with Na, and the presence of distinct doublet peaks at higher Da in the mass spectrum, which minimizes peak overlap and facilitates accurate compositional analysis. These advantages make Ag a better alternative to coatings like Cr, particularly in the context of SIB materials.

By *in situ* coating with Ag, we have demonstrated that it is possible to accurately and reliably measure multi-component materials having large differences in the evaporation field without ambiguity. This will enable the future analysis of cycled electrode and electrolyte materials to investigate

chemical compositional heterogeneity, transition metal dissolution, stress-induced de-localization, and mechanical failure.

Looking ahead, further refinement of cryogenic APT sample preparation will be crucial for enabling near-atomic-scale characterization of both existing and emerging battery chemistries. While *in situ* metallic coating via cryo-FIB is a powerful approach, the selection of a coating material must be carefully tailored to the material under consideration. For instance, Ag is unsuitable for Li-rich systems as there is a risk of outward diffusion of Li in the Ag coatings, potentially forming intermetallics and altering surface composition. Similar precautions are warranted when analyzing Sn- or Zn-based electrodes. Additionally, sputtering parameters such as beam current should be carefully controlled to ensure conformal coating and avoid tip bending. It is also essential to choose coating materials with an evaporation field comparable to that of the underlying sample to prevent local magnification effects at the interface.

Availability of Data and Materials

The authors have declared that no datasets apply for this piece.

Supplementary Material

To view supplementary material for this article, please visit <https://doi.org/10.1093/mam/ozaf041>.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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